

compu-micro-bioinfo-molecu-net

A blog by Ben Vezina.

- **Scope:** bioinformatics, microbiology, molecular biology, papers and other science-related things.
- **Content:** Thoughts, code, tutorials, resources.

Check out the posts [here](#).

The extremely high-value and sought-after logo for compu-micro-bioinfo-molecu-net.

About me

I am a research scientist in microbiology and infectious diseases. I am an expert in molecular biology, microbiology and computational biology/bioinformatics. I love doing science as a day job, in particular analysing and visualising data while learning as many techniques and strats as possible. I've spent a lot of time looking at bacterial pathogens and how they transmit, along with their evolution, metabolism and resistance. My main focus is developing strategies to prevent and limit the spread of antimicrobial resistance through vaccine design, novel antimicrobial discovery, gene technologies and genomic surveillance.

I currently work as a postdoc at the [Department of Infectious Diseases](#), Monash University (2020-Current).

You can find me on Bluesky @[bananabenana.bsky.social](#)

Academic cred

If you want to check out my academic work and contributions to science:

- [Google Scholar](#)
- [OpenAlex](#)
- [ORCID](#)
- [GitHub](#)

Previous gigs

- Consulting for the agricultural biotechnology sector (2020-Current)
- Postdoc at the [Griffith Institute for Drug Discovery](#) (2019-2020)
- PhD from Monash University (2014-2018)
 - [Australian Centre for Disease Preparedness](#), CSIRO
 - [Department of Microbiology](#), Monash University
 - [School of Science](#), RMIT University
- Honours from Deakin University (2013-2014)
 - [Australian Centre for Disease Preparedness](#), CSIRO
 - [School of Medicine](#), Deakin University
- [One-pager resume](#) for other

How to cite and reader info

If for some reason you feel the urge to respond to one of these posts, just leave an [issue](#).

Inspo and motivation

Starting this blog was motivated by a yearning for >300 character-self-expression in a semi-professional context, while providing a potentially useful resource for other scientists or dabbling computational biologists. I was inspired by the informative and enjoyable blogs of several peers. The blog title is inspired by the Marge Simpson-suggested [Compu-Global-Hyper-Mega-Net](#), because *what am I gonna call my [blog]? All the good names are taken.*

Credit: The Simpsons (and whoever owns them now).

Meme-tier disclaimer

This blog is not affiliated with any of my current or past employers, nor does it represent their views etc. I'm not even sure it represents my views. Let's find out together.

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